

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

Project “Into-Dialogue”

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

More than a Dialogue between actors, seeking
the integration of soil-based principles in
agroecological systems

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PURPOSE: The adoption of agroecological approaches is currently relatively limited to pioneering farmers and farmer associations in the EJP-Soil countries (included Turkey); and although the **PRACTICES** are being stimulated through the European Union (EU) Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) and regulations in Turkey, the implementation of sustainable agroecological **SYSTEMS** is until now not promoted by specific policies in these territories. The Into-DIALOGUE project has sought to identify why the **conjunction** of various **practices**, which farmers are already selectively implementing, is complicated and slow to combine as a whole, and **on a landscape or a territorial scale** (which would constitute a **System**). Does it depend on the ecological identity of the farmers? Of the slowness in the development of policies and measures? Of the characteristics of the farms?... The objectives of Into-DIALOGUE fully fit with the wider EJP Soil project “Towards climate-smart sustainable management of agricultural soils”.

INTENDED AUDIENCE: This document is **relevant for** researchers working on soil science, and those scientists specialised in consumer preferences related to the consumption of organic products; for farmers and farmland owners; for decision-makers involved in land-use planning, environmental management or policy development; for policy makers working at a local, regional and national scale, and land-managers responsible for agricultural land.

DESCRIPTION OF THE MAIN ACTIVITIES: The project has focused on analysing, among other aspects, farms characteristics and farmers' knowledge related to sustainable soil management practices and the effectiveness of public policies, as well as their gaps, in Spain, Italy, Czech Republic, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia and Turkey.

KEY RESULTS: Agroecological practices stimulated by the CAP and Turkish regulations cover the farm to crop system and landscape scale, and contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture; soil conservation, including the enhancement of soil fertility through carbon sequestration; improvement of the use and management of water together with water saving; creation, conservation and restoration of habitats favourable to biodiversity; and reduction of the risks and impacts of pesticide and antimicrobial use, among others. But these practices **must be understood on a territorial scale, given the great diversity of management models, depending on ownership structure, farm characteristics, soils type, crop diversity, national/regional regulations, etc.:**

Related to all this, the most important RESULTS of Into-DIALOGUE focus on:

- **The need to know the whole ‘territorial reality’.** The first step, in order for the application of agroecological practices to have territorial resonance, is to know **the ownership structure of a given territory and the soil agricultural practices they are implementing:** 7.5 % of the EU's farms were of 50 ha or more in size and worked two-thirds (68.2 %) of the EU's utilised agricultural area (UAA). This is very significant (Figure 1). In Turkey ownership is more widely distributed (Figure 2).

Figure 1: Distribution of EU farms and Utilised Agricultural Area according to farm size (% , 2020). Source: [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Farms and farmland in the European Union - statistics](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Farms_and_farmland_in_the_European_Union_-_statistics)

Figure 2: Percentage of farms and ha (%) related to farm size (ha) in Turkey.

Source: <https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Tarimsal-Isletme-Yapi-Arastirmasi-2016-24869>

Practices well integrated in the EU and Turkey are organic fertilisation, reduced tillage, drip irrigation, biological pest control, and cultivar choice; and among **the poorly integrated are** biofertilisers; natural pesticides; crop choice and rotations; intercropping and relay intercropping; agroforestry with timber, fruit, or nut trees; direct seeding into living cover crops or mulch; and integration of semi-natural landscape elements at field and farm or their management at landscape scale. The integration of these practices is encouraged by the governments of the EU Member States, through agri-environment-climate payments and environmental investment support co-financed by Pillar 2 of the CAP, according to compliance with these very specific farming practices or technologies (Regulation EU 2020/2220).

In 2023 the total CAP expenditure was 57.5 billion €; in the year 2024, the CAP expenditure for Greening was 8.7 billion €, and for RD environment/climate 3.6 billion €; in total: 12.3 billion € (Figure 3).

Figure 3: CAP expenditure and CAP reform path. Source: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/data-and-analysis/financing/cap-expenditure_en

However, and despite the €12.3 billion € for Greening and RD environment/climate, **only 10.1% of the agricultural soil is considered Healthy**. The other 89.9% is considered to be affected by at least one of the soil threats listed in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Soil degradation processes affecting European Union soils. Only 10.1% of agricultural soils are considered Healthy. Source: <https://esdac.jrc.ec.europa.eu/content/soil-degradation-indicators-eu>

Concerning the **drivers or barriers** to farmers' acceptance of soil-based agroecological management practices, the project reinforces the importance of feedback (dialogue) with farmers, politicians, managers, advisory services, consumers, and other stakeholders involved, in order to understand the situation of European agricultural soils management (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Meetings with different categories of stakeholders have been held in all Into-DIALOGUE countries.

One of the most important objectives of Into-DIALOGUE has been **to understand farmers' soil related needs, as well as their willingness and level of awareness regarding the adoption of sustainable agroecological practices**. But each participating country has different farming conditions, farm sizes, or specialization. Market conditions and financial support (subsidies) are also different. In addition to meetings and interviews in the field, a **questionnaire** was prepared and distributed in the seven countries participating in the project. Among the biggest motivations that would attract the adoption of agroecological practices among farmers are:

- increasing the prosperity of the farm through greater market opportunities
- and financial support from various types of subsidies

However, the analysis highlights **significant barriers** to the adoption of agroecological practices among farmers, including:

- **limited financial resources to acquire new technologies,**

- **the age structure of farm owners,**
- **lack of training and support,**
- **resistance to changing conventional methods:** the fear of introducing new technologies, and, consequently, the potential loss of traditional markets
- A notable proportion of farmers still express **scepticism** about the effectiveness of these practices and face challenges related to market access and equipment compatibility.

• **Where lies the complexity of implementing integrated policies in soil-based agro-ecological systems; and the options for developing EU strategies and actions in national sectoral-policies?** Policy decisions and the agro-ecological practices promoted by these policies are not supported by robust evidence regarding the extent of soil-related issues at the territorial level. Moreover, they frequently lack rigorous conditionality requirements, posing a risk to their effectiveness, particularly in certain types of farming systems. In a brief summary:

- The conditionality requirements which underpin the CAP in the EU countries (or IPARD in Türkiye) play a really **crucial role** for the sustainability of agriculture.
- However, the analysis of Statutory Management Requirements (SMRs) and Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions (GAECs) has revealed a high degree of arbitrariness and ambiguity in their implementation. **Coherent and robust conditionality requirements were found especially for soil health issues** which directly affect soil productivity (i.e., soil erosion), **while more uncertain and dissimilar conditionality requirements were found for other soil health issues.**
- In addition, **shortcomings in compliance with the European environmental directives have contributed to jeopardising land management plans in protected areas and river basin management plans**, including rules to protect soil and landscape.
- we emphasise, **the need to ensure compliance with environmental directives and the application of clearer and less flexible conditionality commitments** at European level as a basic rule for the definition of any national or regional soil strategy.

RESEARCH AND TECHNICAL IMPLICATIONS: Where are the gaps in research? Through a comprehensive literature review, it is concluded that:

- There is an emergent need to establish datasets including physical, chemical, and biological properties useful to assess soil quality and implement the current needs related to soil functions and ecosystem services.
- There is the need to work on the harmonization and clarification of the methodological aspects that are necessary for the correct monitoring of soil biological quality.
- In fact, biological indicators give an integrated overview for soil assessment that only physical and chemical properties cannot provide.
- Finally, agroecological practices have a strong positive effect on soil quality and it is necessary to increase long-term experiments and economically promote their use to enhance the efforts of change management, especially in sensitive environmental areas of Europe.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS: Close attention needs to be paid to the dysfunction between the budget allocated by the CAP to the fulfilment of environmental obligations by agricultural landowners, and the outcome of scientific research related to the health of agricultural soils. The great diversity of situations at territorial and landscape level makes it necessary to adapt European Union and Turkish policies to the local level.

CONCLUSION: The study of the agricultural soils aimed at their protection and conservation through sustainable agriculture absolutely needs the opinions (DIALOGUE) of stakeholders, and, very importantly, the collaboration of the large landowners (who work 68.2 % of the EU's Utilised Agricultural Area). Their views need to reflect the whole 'territorial reality', given the great diversity of management models, depending on ownership structure, farm characteristics, crops type, national/regional regulations, etc. The different national soil health strategies are generally still characterised by weaknesses, partly due to the flexibility with which EU regulations and directives can be implemented. The success of these strategies depends on the ability to adapt macro-policies to the actual territorial micro-policies, which are the only possible tool for their implementation.